

EVALUATION OF THE INFLUENCE OF PREOPERATIVE PLANNING DURING ENDOPROSTHETICS IN PATIENTS WITH DYSPLASTIC COXAROTROSIS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10183622>

Introduction. Adequate preoperative planning using modern instrumental diagnostic methods, templates during surgery, and the use of precision instruments is the key to successful endoprosthetics [1,2]. However, the most accurate installation of endoprosthesis components with orientation to the anatomical axis of the limb, which can eliminate problems during endoprosthetics coxavar or coxavalga with full compensation of ante- or retroversion angles, and reduction to the correct rotation angle, is the main task of preoperative planning [3,4,5].

The aim is to evaluate the effectiveness of preoperative planning using the proposed protractor.

The research material was 142 patients with dysplastic coxarthrosis, of which the main group consisted of 52 patients operated on using the proposed method, the control group - 90 patients operated on with traditional methods, for the period from 2015 to 2021. The obtained indicators were compared with the normal values of the range of motion of the hip joint given in the manual by V.S. Marx, according to which "abduction/adduction" was normal 40° - 0° - 40° , "flexion/extension" was normal 180° - 0° - 10° , "internal/external rotation" was normal 25° - 0° - 25° , and were scored from 0 to 45 points.

The range of motion in the deformed hip joint during "abduction/adduction" before endoprosthetics in the main group was 15° and 15° respectively. This indicator in the main group was established in 3 (15%) patients with II - III, in 15 (65%) with III - IV degrees of severity of dysplasia, in the control group - in 35 (58%) with III - IV, and in all 39 (100%) patients with IV severity of dysplasia. And after the operation, the indicator was almost normal and amounted to 40° - 0° - 40° .

When "flexion/extension", the range of motion in the deformed hip joint before surgery in the main group was 45° in 2 (10%) patients with II - III, 10 (43%) with III - IV, 15 (79%) with IV degrees severity of dysplasia, and in the control group - in 42 (70%) with III - IV, in 17 (85%) with IV severity of

dysplasia. After endoprosthesis, in all patients in the study groups, the amplitude increased to 180° - 0° - 10° .

In a comparative study, it was found that the proposed device allows for effective preoperative planning of endoprosthesis, makes it possible to adequately install an acetabular component of the appropriate size, while determining the length of the lower edge of the true acetabulum, its degree and the point of rimming.

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